

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE ENGINEERS MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

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English the concept of "competence". dictionary in terms of directly means "ability". represents _ Content while " in activity theoretical of knowledge efficient use, high level professional skill, skill and talent to be able to show ". to lighting service does [4].

ABSTRACT

The concept of " competence " . essence . Market relations conditions work in the market priority place occupied strong to competition durable to be each one from an expert professional to competence have to be, him consistent respectively by increasing to go requirement is doing Well, competence what ? Professional competence basically how adjectives reflection is enough ? Teacher in itself how competence qualities light up take necessary _ The same in place that's it and that's it approach ideas on the surface word is maintained [3].

Introduction

In society education system the strategic direction of development is the intellectual and moral development of a person based on purposeful independent activity in various fields. It is important to encourage independent education in the process of educational reforms in our country as well as in the developed countries of the world. direction as is coming [1]. The research of the phenomenon of education of the professional competence of the pedagogue is expressed in the works of a number of scientists. These authors put forward the idea that together with the qualities of professional competence - reliability characterize the teacher's pedagogical culture as a professional - individual phenomenon. In turn, the concept of professional competence, as stated by VASlastenin, represents the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the pedagogue to carry out pedagogical activities, and his professional formed describes [2].

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The concept of "competence". education to the field of psychologists scientific research as a result come in came _ Psychological point of view from the point of view competence "Unconventional circumstances, unexpected cases of the specialist himself how behavior, communication entry, opponents with mutually in relationships new road behavior is uncertain tasks in execution, to conflicts full from the data consistent in use developed going and complicated in processes movement to the plan "ownership". means [5].

Professional competence is a high level of practical application of the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist.

each one independent direction according to integrative knowledge and of actions to be assimilated mean holds _ Also competence _ specialty knowledge always get rich to go, new information learning is important social requirements understand to receive, new information looking for find them _ again work and own in the activity apply to know requirement is enough

Professional competence the following cases obvious manifestation will be :

- i. in complex processes;
- ii. certain tasks;
- iii. using conflicting information;
- iv. in being able to have a plan of action in an unexpected situation.

Professional to competence have expert :

- i. consistently enriches his knowledge;
- ii. learns new information;
- iii. deeply understands the requirements of the era;
- iv. seeks new knowledge;

processes them and uses them effectively in his practical work.

Below professional competence basically reflection doer of adjectives essence briefly is highlighted [6].

1. Social competence - social in relationships activity show skills, qualifications ownership, professional in action subjects with to communicate enter get _

2. Special competence - professional and pedagogical activity organize to do preparation, professional-pedagogical tasks reasonable solution doing, activity realistic assessment of the results, BKM consistent by developing to go is this _ competence mainly psychological, methodical, informative, creative, innovative and communicative competence to the eye thrown away They are in itself the following content represents :

1) psychological competence - pedagogical in progress healthy psychological environment create get, students and education of the process another participants with positive communication organize reach, various negative psychological conflicts own on time understand get and to eliminate ; _

2) methodical competence - pedagogical the process Methodical in terms of reasonable organize education _ _ or educational activity forms right designation, method and tools to the goal according to choose get, methods efficient apply get the tools successful use _

3) informative competence - information in the environment necessary, important, necessary, useful information search, collect, sort, re work and of them targeted, appropriate, effective use _

4) creative competence - pedagogical to the activity relatively critical and creative approach, own creativity qualifications ownership be able to demonstrate ;

5) innovative competence - pedagogical the process improvement, education quality improvement, education of the process efficiency to increase circle new ideas before push them _ to practice successful app reach _

6) communicative competence - education of the process all participants, including students _ with sincere in communication to be, them listen to know them positive effect show get _

7. Personal competence is consistent respectively professional to grow achievement, qualification degree by increasing go, professional in action own internal opportunities manifestation to do

8. Technological competence - professional-pedagogical BKM enriching advanced technologies appropriation, modern tool, technique and from technologies use get _

9. Extreme competence is exceptional situations (natural disasters, technological process from work out) in, pedagogical disputes surface when it comes reasonable decision acceptance to do, right movement qualification ownership _

Teacher of scientists in their work competence pedagogical point of view from the point of view more wider and carefully learning enable giving different aspects and structural parts separate received and by learning developed [7].

SE Shishov by of competence the following definitions cited :

- reading learning because of occupied knowledge, experience, values and to inclinations based on common ability ;

knowledge and situations between contact install to know ability, to problem suitable coming solution reach the way find (competence that to say for something one in the situation manifestation to be done just in case allowed will be

Future occupation education of the teacher professional competence formation pedagogues in preparation complicated problems in line to himself special place holds _ Especially education modernization with depends of reforms current stage professional pedagogical to the activity adaptation problem more obvious manifestation is happening Future occupation education teachers practical, psychological, methodological, research types with one in line occupation education his teacher professional competence formation with rich is going on [8].

Professional competence diagnosis professional of formation essential characteristics diagnostic, communicative, management and projective studies groups input it is necessary The teacher to know activity a lot in terms of being studied of things complexity, dynamics, non-standard, social events separate standing of borders influence them _ search, uncertainty with is determined _ while observation, interlocutor internal the world modeling qualification mean holds _ This is it without self in order put features own knowledge and qualifications always improvement necessity, another to people directed own behavior strict coordination study with is described .

The teacher professional upbringing ability research to do dedicated in the works his the following types with difference will be :

- special upbringing competence - professional activities enough high level possession, own upcoming professional development design ability ;

- social upbringing ability - joint professional activity, cooperation and as well as this in the book acceptance done professional communication styles possession, own professional job results for social responsibility [9].

Profession education of the teacher professional competence, voluntary qualities, intellectual potential, emotional adjectives, practical skills, self administration get abilities mutually dependence and of the person socio-cultural activity degree reflection individual qualities that cause based on is formed .

In the formation of professional competence, a desire for full professional formation,

perception of pedagogical technological situations, including the ability to expand the scope of professional interests, is a demand for self-improvement. Most students develop a deep and persistent interest in professional knowledge, skills, competences and abilities and their manifestation .

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